

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ELECTRICITY FROM THE FROST

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Abstract

The subject of the article is to demonstrate the capabilities of “Green Energy” in the form of a simple technical device for generating electrical energy. Moreover, the device has no moving parts, is very reliable in operation and can be used without human service in remote places on Earth with a harsh climate.

The use of the described generators will solve the problems of power supply for many consumers, as well as provide support to existing capacities.

The introduction and use of such generators will significantly reduce consumers’ dependence on fossil fuels and eliminate the need to build power lines, which will have a positive impact on the environment as a whole.

Keywords: green energy, ecology, carbon dioxide emissions, geothermal energy, low-potential energy source, heat pump, autonomous power supply.

It is difficult to overestimate the relevance of green energy in the modern world. The problems of using fossil fuels and the dangers of using nuclear energy make scientists and inventors look for new sources of energy or to improve those already available. However, alternative energy sources cannot always be used in different regions of the earth. For example, solar panels are useless in regions where there is polar night for half a year, and wind generators are pointless in the absence of wind.

I would like to present to your attention an original device for generating electrical energy due to the difference in temperature of the soil (or water) and the environment.

Electrical energy is generated by thermoelectric assembly (TEC), which today can be produced with very high efficiency. And the delivery of soil or water heat to the fuel and energy complex is carried out using thermosiphon technology.

Design.

The main element of the thermoelectric generator is a two-phase, vapor-liquid thermosiphon (1), which forms a circulation circuit for the coolant (refrigerant). The thermosiphon has a vertical tubular body, the lower end of which forms the evaporation zone (2) of the circulation circuit, and the upper end forms the condensation zone (3). In this case, between zones (2) and (3) there is a transit section (4). The housing is made coaxial in such a way that its inner part (5) (inner tube) ensures the flow of coolant liquid from the condensation zone (3) into the evaporation zone (2), and the outer part (6) (between the inner and outer tubes) ensures the rise saturated coolant vapor from the evaporation zone (2) to the condensation zone (3). The evaporation zone (2) (lower end of the body) is located in the deep layer of the earth's shell (in soil or water), and the condensation zone (3) (upper end of the body) is located in the above-ground part, in contact with atmospheric air and having a lower temperature than soil (water).

pic.1. Design

The thermosiphon body is partially filled with a coolant, which can be used, for example, ammonia or carbon dioxide. The evaporation temperature of the coolant should be between the temperatures of the deep layers and atmospheric air.

To maintain the temperature difference between zones (2) and (3), a heat shield (7) made of heat-insulating plates is installed in the soil (water) or on its surface. In this case, the thermosiphon body itself is covered with a layer of thermal insulation (8).

In the condensation zone there are branches (9) in the form of several tubes. The said branches (9) are equipped with external fins (10), which form heat exchangers cooled by outside air. In this case, between the fins (10) and the inner part of the branch (9) there are several thermoelectric converters (11) (TEC), which are connected by conductors (12) to the matching device (13) of the electrical energy consumer installed under the heat shield (7). The use of branches (9) makes it possible to more efficiently use the temperature difference by increasing the contact area of the converters (11) with the fins (10).

Principle of operation.

The thermosiphon (1) of the generator is installed in the ground in a well (14) or partially immersed in a reservoir on a float (not shown in the figures). The coolant circulation in the thermosiphon body is realized due to gravitational heat exchange. The upper end of the housing (condensation zone 3) is cooler because it is cooled and blown by outside air, while the lower end (evaporation zone 4) has a higher temperature. In the condensation zone (3), saturated coolant vapor condenses on the inner walls of the housing and, under the

influence of gravity, flows down into the evaporation zone (2) along the inner part (5) of the housing. In this case, in the lower part (evaporation zone 2), the coolant evaporates and the resulting steam, due to the pressure drop in the condensation zone (3), moves upward along the outer part (6), etc. As a result of circulation in the condensation zone (2), a temperature difference occurs on the thermoelectric converter (11), located between the “cold” fins (10) blown by air and the “hot” coolant vapor inside the housing. This phenomenon leads to the generation of EMF on the converter (12) due to the Seebeck effect. The resulting energy is transferred to the matching device (13) of the consumer.

pic.2. TEC

Thus, the design of the claimed device allows for the generation of electrical energy due to a small temperature difference between the soil (water) and the outside air without burning fuel and thermal waste, as well as without emitting harmful exhaust gases and radiation. Moreover, the operation of the device does not depend on natural wind, solar radiation or natural water

movement. The device can be used in conditions of snow cover and deep freezing of the soil in hard-to-reach places in the absence of power supply

At the moment, thermosiphons are used to remove parasitic heat in order to stabilize the soils of foundations on permafrost, while energy is completely wasted

in the atmosphere, although it could bring practical benefit. It would be quite enough to power communications or automation equipment during a period when other alternative energy sources are unavailable (long polar night or lack of wind).

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